

Engineering and Social Impact: Student Perceptions of Competencies for Social Entrepreneurship

Afsaneh Hamedí d'Escoffier¹, Luiz Ney d'Escoffier¹, Frederico Pifano de Rezende^{2,3}

¹ Laboratório de Protozoologia, Instituto Oswaldo Cruz, Fiocruz, Rio de Janeiro, Brasil

² Texas A&M University, Texas, USA

³ Instituto Federal do Espírito Santo, Espírito Santo, Brasil

Email: afsanehamedí@gmail.com; lescof@ioc.fiocruz.br; fredpifano@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15847200>

Abstract

This study aims to deepen the understanding of engineering students' perspectives on the competencies required for social entrepreneurship. While entrepreneurship drives development through innovation and economic growth, social entrepreneurship goes further by balancing social impact and financial sustainability. Social entrepreneurs operate in for-profit, non-profit, or hybrid organizations, requiring personal, business, and managerial competencies. In addition to traditional skills like innovation and risk-taking, virtues, collaboration, and empathy are essential. Although universities have invested in entrepreneurial education, research on social entrepreneurship remains limited, gaining prominence only in the past decade. Our study seeks to understand engineering students' perceptions of these competencies through a qualitative approach, using thematic analysis of open-ended responses. The study involved 48 engineering students from Texas A&M University, USA. Preliminary results indicate a multidimensional perspective, emphasizing resilience and risk-taking—competencies associated with traditional entrepreneurship. Business success emerged as the primary concern, with adaptability and courage considered essential. In contrast, social aspects were deemed less important, with social awareness—a core competency of social entrepreneurship—ranked as insignificant. Justifications reflect a belief that success depends on individual talent and that inclusion is not essential for a company. This suggests that students view entrepreneurship solely through a profit-driven lens, disregarding its social impact. To broaden the analysis, we will apply the same methodology to students at the University of Brasília, Brazil, who experience a different reality and lack formal entrepreneurship courses in engineering. By comparing these perspectives, we aim to outline the role of universities in shaping engineers' competencies for social entrepreneurship and explore connections between curriculum design and competency development. Ultimately, we hope to contribute to discussions on how engineering education can foster skills geared toward social development.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, competence, sustainability, undergraduate.

1 Introduction

Addressing social challenges such as housing, healthcare, and education for marginalized communities requires innovative approaches beyond governmental and traditional business solutions. Social entrepreneurship has emerged as a response to these unmet needs, gaining recognition in the 1980s and 1990s through the contributions of Bill Drayton and Charles Leadbeater (Dornelas, 2001), despite entrepreneurship itself being rooted in economic theory since Schumpeter (1911).

At its core, social entrepreneurship involves identifying and leveraging opportunities to generate social value. While Certo and Miller (Certo & Miller, 2008) define it as a structured process of opportunity recognition, Steinerowski and cols. (Steinerowski, Jack & Farmer, 2008; Dacin, Dacin & Matear, 2010; Nga & Shamuganathan, 2010) emphasize its financial sustainability model, where profits are reinvested to enhance social impact. Lubberink (Lubberink, 2019) further highlights the ability of social entrepreneurs to pinpoint systemic failures and develop innovative, yet often complex, solutions that require effective management strategies.

Entrepreneurial competencies are essential for tackling social issues and advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN, 2015). McClelland (McClelland, 1973) conceptualizes competence as a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, while Brinkmann (Brinkmann, 2007) expands this notion to encompass social, technical, and psychological attributes. In social entrepreneurship, competencies such as social innovation, leadership, strategic management, empathy, sustainability orientation, and emotional intelligence play a decisive role in success (Vázquez-Parra, García-González & Ramírez-Montoya, 2021).

Despite growing recognition of the need for education in social entrepreneurship, there remains a lack of standardized curricula and pedagogical strategies to effectively develop these competencies (Pittaway & Cope, 2007; Alourhzal & Hattabou, 2021). Research indicates that students often perceive deficiencies in their training, particularly concerning social innovation and business management (Cruz-Sandoval, Vázquez-Parra & Alonso-Galicia, 2022).

This study is part of a broader research project that employs Q methodology. Contribute to the field by examining which entrepreneurial competencies are most valued by students and educators in engineering education, applying Q methodology in two distinct educational contexts (Stephenson, 1935; Watts & Stenner, 2012). While Q methodology has been employed in general entrepreneurship research, its application in social entrepreneurship remains underexplored (Qureshi, Bhatt & Riaz, 2012; Bhatt, Qureshi & Riaz, 2019). By addressing this gap, the study aims to inform the design of educational strategies that foster key skills and values essential for social entrepreneurship, ultimately promoting sustainable development.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research context and participants

The data collection took place over two consecutive semesters at Texas A&M University (TAMU) in the course *Enterprise Basics for Technical Entrepreneurs*. This is an elective course offered by the Department of Multidisciplinary Engineering through the *Meloy Program in Engineering, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship*, which aims to foster an entrepreneurial perspective among engineering students.

The group of 68 students who responded voluntarily to the questionnaire came from at least 10 different engineering programs out of the 26 offered at TAMU. The course is offered regularly each semester and, since it has no prerequisites, it is open to both undergraduate and graduate students.

Most of these students have only a technical engineering background, with little or no prior knowledge of entrepreneurship. The course's primary goal is to introduce students to business-related content and encourage an entrepreneurial mindset. There is no specific research on this, but the actual intention to start a business is estimated to be below 10% at the beginning of the semester. The data was collected within the first month of the course.

2.2 Research design

As part of a larger study, participants were asked to rank a series of statements related to social entrepreneurship competencies, organizing them from most to least important. The study primarily employs Q methodology as its research design (for more details on Q methodology, visit: <https://qmethod.org/>). Additionally, it incorporates open-ended questions, allowing students to elaborate on their reasoning for prioritizing certain competencies over others and to suggest additional competencies they believe should be integrated into their education.

The qualitative data, collected from 48 students, underwent manual thematic analysis using an inductive approach. Responses were categorized based on the competencies they referenced, while the justifications provided were examined to identify underlying reasoning patterns and assess the coherence between the selected competency and the accompanying explanation. This analysis was then used to construct a qualitative profile of the student groups, offering insights into their perceptions of the engineer's role in social entrepreneurship.

3 Results

The results indicate that students most valued the competencies of risk-taking and resilience, both linked to traditional entrepreneurship. Although other competencies were mentioned, their relevance was not statistically significant. Notably, 81% of students prioritized traditional entrepreneurship competencies, showing a strong preference for business creation and growth focused on economic value.

Conversely, 69% of students devalued competencies related to social entrepreneurship, with social awareness most frequently cited as less important. This highlights a market-oriented mindset, with little emphasis on generating positive social impact.

These findings suggest that engineering students tend to favor competitiveness and financial sustainability over social innovation and sustainable development. This likely reflects the traditional focus of engineering curricula on technical efficiency and economic viability, shaping how students perceive their professional role in society.

The following sections analyze students' justifications for their choices, offering deeper insights into their views on entrepreneurship's impact on their careers.

3.1 Risk-taking

This competency was rated as the most relevant by students, reflecting an orientation aligned with traditional entrepreneurship. Its importance is associated with business growth and success, facilitating entry into new markets, the development of innovative products, and the ability to strategically face competition. The emphasis placed by students suggests a predominantly business creation and expansion-oriented perspective, prioritizing the maximization of opportunities and economic sustainability.

This result indicates a strong appreciation for competitive strategies and innovation as essential elements for business success. In the context of traditional entrepreneurship, the pursuit of market differentiation and operational efficiency are key factors for business longevity. Thus, the prioritization of this competency by students reflects an understanding of market dynamics and the need for continuous adaptation to ensure a competitive advantage.

The justifications provided reinforce this perspective, highlighting the concern for business success from a strategic, market-oriented approach, as demonstrated in the following information:

"The whole essence of entrepreneurship is in my opinion learning and creating opportunity. By being willing to fail, you can maximize validated learning."

"Having the courage to fail or being risk tolerant allows entrepreneurs to try novel ideas. Without risk, there is very little that would set entrepreneurs apart."

"Entrepreneurs must be perseverant and willing the failure before filing their success. Without this, all others would not matter because they will turn away at the first sign of trouble".

3.2 Resilience

The second competency highlighted by students was resilience, also linked to traditional entrepreneurship. This competency can be defined as the ability to face daily challenges, overcome obstacles, and maintain adaptability in the face of adversity, being especially crucial in the early years of a company—a period characterized by greater instability and uncertainty.

Resilience plays a fundamental role in business sustainability, allowing entrepreneurs to learn from failures, adjust strategies, and remain operational even in the face of financial, structural, or market difficulties. The ability to recover and adapt not only mitigates the impact of crises but also strengthens the company's competitive position in the long term.

The justifications provided by students reinforce this perspective, emphasizing that the ability to handle and learn from mistakes is essential for business success, as demonstrated below:

"Every entrepreneur will fail at some point, it is how they handle those failures that determine whether or not the company will become successful"

"An entrepreneur needs to be able to handle risks of unforeseen changes as they will come no matter what"

"The ability to adapt to change is the feature that separate it from operation. Entrepreneurship is inherently an uncertain endeavor. Without grit, one is set to fail any entrepreneurial undertaking"

3.3 Social awareness

When analyzing the competencies rated as least important by students, it becomes evident that social awareness was the most frequently devalued. This competency is strongly associated with social entrepreneurship, as it involves the ability to recognize social and environmental challenges and proactively work toward sustainable solutions. However, the justifications provided indicate that students do not consider it essential for business success, particularly regarding social inclusion.

The students' statements reflect a pragmatic view of entrepreneurship, prioritizing aspects that directly impact business growth and competitiveness. Social inclusion is perceived as secondary or even irrelevant to idea generation and business expansion. The following justifications illustrate this perspective:

"Inclusion is not particularly important, talent + skill is."

"Although inclusion is important both ethically and morally and can sometimes be useful to the company, it does not directly lead to better company growth, idea generation, or an innovative mindset as well as the other items."

These statements reveal a mindset strongly focused on financial performance and innovation, to the detriment of ethical and social values. Business success is positioned as the absolute priority, surpassing considerations of social impact or corporate responsibility. This result suggests that, for these students, entrepreneurship should be primarily guided by economic metrics, relegating social awareness to a peripheral or even dispensable role in the business context.

4 Discussion

The results highlight a misalignment between the competencies valued by engineering students and those essential for social entrepreneurship. While traditional competencies like resilience and risk-taking were prioritized, students gave little importance to social awareness, empathy, and systemic vision, reflecting a predominantly market-oriented view of entrepreneurship based on individual talent and financial success.

This tendency is linked to the structure of engineering curricula, which emphasize technical efficiency and economic viability, limiting students' understanding of engineering's role in addressing social challenges. The literature confirms that engineering education often underestimates the importance of hybrid business models that balance profit and social impact.

To address this, a holistic curricular approach is needed, one that combines management tools with values like social responsibility and sustainability. Active learning methods such as PBL and PjBL can foster a mindset more oriented toward social problem-solving, but their effectiveness depends on the intentional integration of social themes, including equity, inclusion, and sustainability.

Interdisciplinary modules involving social sciences, economics, and impact management can enhance students' preparedness for complex social entrepreneurship contexts. The planned research expansion to the University of Brasília (UnB), where no formal entrepreneurship courses exist in engineering, will allow comparison between educational realities and inform strategies for better competency integration.

These findings reinforce the urgency of curriculum reforms that embed social entrepreneurship as a core component of engineering education. Frameworks like CDIO and UNESCO's Engineering for Sustainable Development provide pathways to align curricula with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Additionally, mandatory interdisciplinary projects and revised learning outcomes, guided by models like EntreComp, can support the development of empathy, systemic thinking, and ethical reasoning.

Such reforms should be accompanied by faculty development, equipping educators to address ethical and social justice issues. Without structural changes, even active methodologies risk reproducing traditional technical approaches under new formats.

In sum, this study advocates a systemic redesign of engineering curricula to make social entrepreneurship integral to professional identity. Expanding the research to the Brazilian context will deepen the debate on preparing engineers to contribute ethically and effectively to social transformation, making a positive impact a central educational commitment rather than an optional goal.

5 Conclusion

This study reveals a significant gap between the competencies valued by engineering students—such as resilience and risk-taking—and those essential for social entrepreneurship, like social awareness and inclusion. Students tend to associate entrepreneurship with financial success and individual ability, reflecting the traditional engineering education focus on technical efficiency and economic viability, and overlooking its social dimension.

Bridging this gap requires rethinking how social entrepreneurship is taught. Active learning methods like PBL and PjBL, along with interdisciplinary approaches that include social sciences, economics, and sustainability, can help students develop a more holistic understanding of entrepreneurship as a driver of social change.

The planned expansion of this research to students at the University of Brasília (UnB)—where formal entrepreneurship training is lacking—will offer comparative insights into how curricular design influences perceptions and preparedness for social entrepreneurship.

Ultimately, universities play a key role in shaping future engineers. By integrating social responsibility into entrepreneurial education, institutions can better equip students to foster sustainable development, promoting a multidimensional view of entrepreneurship that balances economic, social, and environmental goals.

References

- Alourhzal, H. & Hattabou, A. (2021). Social entrepreneurship education: a systematic review curricula contents and teaching methods, *African Scientific Journal*, 3(7), 001-022.
- Bhatt, B., Qureshi, I. & Riaz, S. (2019). Social entrepreneurship in non-munificent institutional environments and implications for institutional work: Insights from China, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 154, 605-630.
- Brinkmann, J. (2007). *The competence of top management teams and success of new technology-based firms*, Wiesbaden: Deutscher Universitätsverlag.
- Certo, S. & Miller, T. (2008). Social entrepreneurship: keys issues and concepts. *Business Horizons*, 51, 267-271.
- Christie, M., & de Graaff, E. (2017). The philosophical and pedagogical underpinnings of Active Learning in Engineering Education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(1), 5-16.
- Cruz-Sandoval, M., Vázquez-Parra, J.C. & Alonso-Galicia, P.E. (2022). Student perception of competencies and skills for social entrepreneurship in complex environments: an approach with Mexican University students, *Social Sciences*, 11(314).
- Dacin, P., Dacin, M. & Matear, M. (2010). Social entrepreneurship: why we don't need a new theory and how we move forward from here. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 38-57.
- Dornelas, J.C.A. (2001). *Empreendedorismo transformando ideias em negócios*. Rio de Janeiro: Campus.
- Edström, K., & Kolmos, A. (2014). PBL and CDIO: complementary models for engineering education development. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 39(5), 539-555.
- Graaff, E. d., & Kolmos, A. (2003). Characteristics of Problem-Based Learning. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 19(5), 657-662.
- Lubberink, R. (2019). Social entrepreneurship and sustainable development in decent work and economic growth. *Encyclopedia of the UN sustainable development goals*, Leal Filho, W; Brandli, L.; Ozuyar, P.; Wall, T (eds). Springer.
- McClelland, D.C. (1973) testing for competence rather than for "intelligence", *American Psychologist*.
- Nga, J. & Shamuganathan, G. (2010). The influence of personality traits and demographic factors on social entrepreneurship startup intentions, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 95, 259-282.
- Pittaway, L., Cope, J. (2007). Entrepreneurship education: a systematic review of the evidence. *National Council for Graduate Entrepreneurship*, Working Paper 002/2006.
- Qureshi, I., Baht B. & Riaz, S. (2012). Objective analysis of subjectivity: Q-methodology for research on social entrepreneurship. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 1, 13375.
- Schumpeter, J.A. (1911). *The theory of economic development*, Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Steinerowski, A., Jack, S. & Farmer, J. (2008). Who are the social entrepreneurs and what do they actually do? *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, 28(21), article 2.
- Stephenson, W. (1935). Correlating persons instead of tests, *Journal of Personality*, 4(1), 17-24.
- Tracey, P., & Phillips, N. (2007). The distinctive challenge of educating social entrepreneurs A postscript to rejoinder to the special issue on entrepreneurship education. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 6: 264-271.
- UN (2015). *Transforming the world: the 2030 agenda for sustainable development*, A/RES/70/1.
- Vázquez-Parra, J.C., García-González, A & Ramírez-Montoya, M.S. (2021). Social Entrepreneurship competency: Na approach by discipline and gender. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 13(5), 1357-1373.
- Watts, S. & Stenner, P. (2012). *Doing Q methodological research: theory, method and interpretation*, London: SAGE Publications Ltd.